

Has infinity come to an end in mathematics?

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Abstract. This paper shows how the infinity of natural numbers can be contradictory within the mathematics.

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1 Finite quantity of natural numbers

Theorem 1.1. *The set N of natural numbers, constructed using the decimal number system, can only have a finite number of elements.*

Proof. In the hypothesis of having a decimal numerical system capable of representing every natural number, without any limit, it is possible to define the following bijective function f between the ordinal ω and the set N :

$$f = \{(n, n) : n \in N\}$$

that allows us to write:

$$\begin{aligned} f(n) &= n & \forall n \in N \\ f^{-1}(n) &= n & \forall n \in N \end{aligned}$$

Since the function f is bijective between the ordinal ω and the set N we can also write:

$$\begin{aligned} \forall x \in \omega \quad \exists! n \in N : & \quad (x, n) \in h_0 \\ \forall n \in N \quad \exists! x \in \omega : & \quad (n, x) \in h_0^{-1} \end{aligned}$$

Let us define as function of the even pairs of the function f that function f_p constituted by the pairs of the function f that have on the right (as images) only even numbers:

$$f_p = \{(2n, 2n) : n \in N\}$$

and that allows us to write:

$$\begin{aligned} f_p(2n) &= 2n \quad \forall n \in N \\ f_p^{-1}(2n) &= 2n \quad \forall n \in N \end{aligned}$$

Since these even pairs are contained in the function f , the following relations will also apply:

$$\begin{aligned} f(2n) &= 2n \quad \forall n \in N \\ f^{-1}(2n) &= 2n \quad \forall n \in N \end{aligned}$$

Always in the hypothesis of having a decimal numerical system capable of representing every natural number, without any limit, it is possible to define the following bijective function h between the ordinal ω and the even numbers of the set N :

$$h = \{(n, 2n) : n \in N\}$$

that allows us to write:

$$\begin{aligned} h(n) &= 2n \quad \forall n \in N \\ h^{-1}(2n) &= n \quad \forall n \in N \end{aligned}$$

Since the function h is bijective between the ordinal ω and the even numbers of the set N , we can also write:

$$\begin{aligned} \forall x \in \omega \quad \exists! p \in 2N : \quad (x, p) \in h \\ \forall p \in 2N \quad \exists! x \in \omega : \quad (p, x) \in h^{-1} \end{aligned}$$

This established we can introduce the following expression:

$$(1) \quad h_0 = h$$

whose validity is ensured by the existence of the function h .

Since the function h is bijective between the ordinal ω and the even numbers of the set N , from (1) we know that also the function h_0 is bijective between the ordinal ω and the even numbers of the set N :

$$\begin{aligned} \forall x \in \omega \quad \exists! p \in 2N : \quad (x, p) \in h_0 \\ \forall p \in 2N \quad \exists! x \in \omega : \quad (p, x) \in h_0^{-1} \end{aligned}$$

Given any two elements a, b belonging to a generic set A , we define with the

symbol $(\ a, b \)$: $A \rightarrow A$ the bijective function which exchanges them:

$$\begin{cases} x \rightarrow x & \text{se } x \neq a, x \neq b \\ x \rightarrow a & \text{se } x = b \\ x \rightarrow b & \text{se } x = a \end{cases}$$

At this point we are able to introduce the following expression:

$$(2) \quad h_{n+1} = h_n[(\ h_n^{-1}(2n), f^{-1}(2n) \)]$$

which gives function h_{n+1} the same identical pairs as function h_n except for the two domain values indicated within the exchange function, which will be inverted with each other.

We prove through the principle of induction that the expression $P(n)$ formed by the following three contemporary relations:

$$\begin{cases} h_{n+1} = h_n[(\ h_n^{-1}(2n), f^{-1}(2n) \)] \\ \forall x \in \omega \quad \exists! p \in 2N: \quad (x, p) \in h_{n+1} \\ \forall p \in 2N \quad \exists! x \in \omega: \quad (p, x) \in h_{n+1}^{-1} \end{cases}$$

is valid for each number n belonging to the set N .

Let's start by seeing that the following expression $P(0)$ is valid:

$$\begin{cases} h_1 = h_0[(\ h_0^{-1}(0), f^{-1}(0) \)] \\ \forall x \in \omega \quad \exists! p \in 2N: \quad (x, p) \in h_1 \\ \forall p \in 2N \quad \exists! x \in \omega: \quad (p, x) \in h_1^{-1} \end{cases}$$

Since the function h_0 is bijective between the ordinal ω and the even numbers of the set N , the inverse function h_0^{-1} will also exist. Since this inverse function acts on all even numbers of set N , it will have the existing value $h_0^{-1}(0)$.

Since the function f is bijective between the ordinal ω and the natural numbers of the set N , the inverse function f^{-1} will also exist. Since this inverse function acts on all the natural numbers of the set N , it will have the existing value $f^{-1}(0)$.

Since finally the value $f^{-1}(0)$ belongs to the ordinal ω , it will also be one of the domain values of the function h_0 .

With this we have verified the validity of the expression that makes us pass from the function h_0 to the function h_1 :

$$h_1 = h_0[(\ h_0^{-1}(0), f^{-1}(0) \)]$$

Moreover, since the passage from the function h_0 to the function h_1 happens with the exchange between only two elements of the domain or between neither of them (in case the two elements to be exchanged should coincide), we will have that also the function h_1 is bijective just like the function h_0 is:

$$\begin{aligned} \forall x \in \omega \quad \exists! p \in 2N : \quad (x, p) \in h_1 \\ \forall p \in 2N \quad \exists! x \in \omega : \quad (p, x) \in h_1^{-1} \end{aligned}$$

Let us consider the following expression $P(j)$ to be valid:

$$\begin{cases} h_{j+1} = h_j[(h_j^{-1}(2j), f^{-1}(2j))] \\ \forall x \in \omega \quad \exists! p \in 2N : \quad (x, p) \in h_{j+1} \\ \forall p \in 2N \quad \exists! x \in \omega : \quad (p, x) \in h_{j+1}^{-1} \end{cases}$$

and prove that the following expression $P(j+1)$ is valid:

$$\begin{cases} h_{j+2} = h_{j+1}[(h_{j+1}^{-1}(2j+2), f^{-1}(2j+2))] \\ \forall x \in \omega \quad \exists! p \in 2N : \quad (x, p) \in h_{j+2} \\ \forall p \in 2N \quad \exists! x \in \omega : \quad (p, x) \in h_{j+2}^{-1} \end{cases}$$

If $P(j)$ is valid, this means that the function h_{j+1} is bijective between the ordinal ω and the even numbers of the set N .

Since the function h_{j+1} is bijective between the ordinal ω and the even numbers of the set N , the inverse function h_{j+1}^{-1} will also exist. Since this inverse function acts on all the even numbers of the set N , being $2j+2$ an even number, it will have the existing value $h_{j+1}^{-1}(2j+2)$.

Since the function f is bijective between the ordinal ω and the numbers of the set N , the inverse function f^{-1} will also exist. Since this inverse function acts on all the natural numbers of the set N , being $2j+2$ a natural number, it will have the existing value $f^{-1}(2j+2)$.

Since finally the value $f^{-1}(2j+2)$ belongs to the ordinal ω , it will also be one of the domain values of the function h_{j+1} .

With this we have verified the validity of the expression that makes us pass from the function h_{j+1} to the function h_{j+2} :

$$h_{j+2} = h_{j+1}[(h_{j+1}^{-1}(2j+2), f^{-1}(2j+2))]$$

Moreover, since the passage from the function h_{j+1} to the function h_{j+2} happens with the exchange between only two elements of the domain or between neither of them (in case the two elements to be exchanged should coincide),

we will have that also the function h_{j+2} is bijective just like the function h_{j+1} is:

$$\begin{aligned} \forall x \in \omega \quad \exists! p \in \mathbb{2}N : \quad (x, p) \in h_{j+2} \\ \forall p \in \mathbb{2}N \quad \exists! x \in \omega : \quad (p, x) \in h_{j+2}^{-1} \end{aligned}$$

Thanks to the principle of induction, we are thus able to consider the following three relations valid at the same time:

$$(3) \quad \begin{cases} h_{n+1} = h_n[(h_n^{-1}(2n), f^{-1}(2n))] \\ \forall x \in \omega \quad \exists! p \in \mathbb{2}N : \quad (x, p) \in h_{n+1} \\ \forall p \in \mathbb{2}N \quad \exists! x \in \omega : \quad (p, x) \in h_{n+1}^{-1} \end{cases}$$

for each number n belonging to the set N .

Let us now analyse in detail what are the characteristics of the first of these three relations:

$$h_{n+1} = h_n[(h_n^{-1}(2n), f^{-1}(2n))]$$

If the domain values of the function h_n that are exchanged in constructing h_{n+1} :

$$h_n^{-1}(2n), f^{-1}(2n):$$

are coincident, namely if it is valid:

$$h_n^{-1}(2n) = f^{-1}(2n):$$

there is no exchange, and we can write:

$$h_{n+1} = h_n$$

The following relation will also be true:

$$h_n[h_n^{-1}(2n)] = h_n[f^{-1}(2n)]:$$

which, with the relation:

$$f^{-1}(2n) = 2n$$

allowing us to write:

$$2n = h_n(2n)$$

So we know that if the two values to be exchanged are the same, the function h_n will have among its pairs also the one that makes the domain $2n$ correspond to the image $2n$, namely the following:

$$2n, 2n$$

which is precisely the generic even pair of the function f .

This means that in correspondence with the function h_{n+1} obtained from the function h_n without making any exchange we can write:

$$(2n, 2n) \in h_{n+1}$$

This function h_{n+1} , being the copy of the function h_n , will also have within itself all the even pairs of the function f already present in the latter.

If the domain values of the function h_n that are exchanged in constructing h_{n+1} are not coincident but distinct, namely if it is valid:

$$h_n^{-1}(2n) \neq f^{-1}(2n):$$

an actual exchange of domain values takes place between two pairs of the function h_n .

The first couple involved in the exchange will be given by:

$$h_n^{-1}(2n), h_n[h_n^{-1}(2n)]$$

that we can write like:

$$h_n^{-1}(2n), 2n$$

whose value on the right is identical to the value on the right in the generic even pair of the function f .

Since the value on the left:

$$h_n^{-1}(2n)$$

is that value within the function h_n that has as image $2n$, the only even pair of the function f of which it could be part is:

$$2n, 2n$$

But that would mean having:

$$h_n^{-1}(2n) = 2n$$

that thanks to the relation:

$$f^{-1}(2n) = 2n$$

becomes:

$$h_n^{-1}(2n) = f^{-1}(2n)$$

Since we are excluding just this case, which occurs only in the absence of exchanges, we know that the value $h_n^{-1}(2n)$ is not part of any even pair of the function f eventually already present within the function h_n .

The second couple involved in the exchange will be given by:

$$f^{-1}(2n), h_n[f^{-1}(2n)]$$

By using the relation:

$$f^{-1}(2n) = 2n$$

we can write the previous pair as:

$$2n, h_n(2n)$$

whose value on the left is identical to the value on the left in the generic even pair of the function f .

Since the value on the right:

$$h_n(2n)$$

is that value within the function h_n that is the image of $2n$, the only even pair of the function f of which it could be part is:

$$2n, 2n$$

But that would mean having:

$$h_n(2n) = 2n$$

and therefore:

$$h_n^{-1}[h_n(2n)] = h_n^{-1}(2n)$$

namely:

$$2n = h_n^{-1}(2n)$$

that thanks to the relation:

$$f^{-1}(2n) = 2n$$

becomes:

$$f^{-1}(2n) = h_n^{-1}(2n)$$

Since we are excluding just this case, which occurs only in the absence of exchanges, we know that the value $h_n(2n)$ is not part of any even pair of the function f eventually already present within the function h_n .

By exchanging the values to the left of the two pairs highlighted here, we obtain a function h_{n+1} that has all the pairs of the function h_n except those taken here in consideration that will be replaced by two others.

The first of the two new pairs that are formed in the function h_{n+1} is as follows:

$$2n, 2n$$

which coincides with the generic even pair of the function f .

The second pair that is formed in the function h_{n+1} is as follows:

$$h_n^{-1}(2n), h_n(2n)$$

Which, we must keep in mind, has been constructed without disjointing any of the even pairs of the function f possibly already present within the function h_n .

Ultimately, in correspondence with the following expression (2) that makes us pass from the function h_n to the function h_{n+1} :

$$h_{n+1} = h_n[(\quad h_n^{-1}(2n), f^{-1}(2n) \quad)]$$

we can write, regardless of whether the two values to be exchanged are distinct

or coincident:

$$(4) \quad (2n, 2n) \in h_{n+1}$$

Since from the expression (2) we have arrived at the expression (4) through passages independent of the value of the number n , and since in the expression (2) the number n can assume all possible values of the set N (because of the principle of induction seen above), we can also extend the expression (4) to all the values of the number n .

This means that if we fix the number n to the value to which the function h_{n+1} refers, it will be true that:

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} (2n-2, 2n-2) \in h_n \\ (2n-4, 2n-4) \in h_{n-1} \\ \dots \\ (2, 2) \in h_2 \\ (0, 0) \in h_1 \end{array} \right.$$

Since these are all the even pairs of the function f that precede the pair:

$$2n, 2n$$

belonging to h_{n+1} , and since the function h_{n+1} is built on the function h_n preserving the values of the even pairs of the function f possibly already contained within it, and since the function h_n is also built on the function h_{n-1} preserving the values of the even pairs of the function f possibly already contained within it, and so on until h_1 we can attribute all the previous values of the even pairs of the function f also to the function h_{n+1} :

$$(5) \quad \left\{ \begin{array}{l} (2n, 2n) \in h_{n+1} \\ (2n-2, 2n-2) \in h_{n+1} \\ (2n-4, 2n-4) \in h_{n+1} \\ \dots \\ (2, 2) \in h_{n+1} \\ (0, 0) \in h_{n+1} \end{array} \right.$$

Since all these relations start with the following expression:

$$h_{n+1} = h_n[(h_n^{-1}(2n), f^{-1}(2n))]]$$

where the number n can assume all the possible values of the set N (because of the induction principle seen above) we can consider them capable of extending for all the even pairs of the function f . Moreover, since all these relations (5) are valid in correspondence of a function h_{n+1} that is fixed and independent of the values assumed by the number n , we can write:

$$\exists m \quad \forall x \in N \quad ((2x, 2x) \in h_m)$$

As a result of this we can consider existing a function h_m that contains all even pairs of the function f . Since this function h_m must be bijective between the ordinal ω and the even numbers of the set N (because of the induction principle seen above), it will have as images all and only the even numbers of the set N . This means that it cannot contain other pairs beyond the even one of the function f , since the latter are already sufficient on their own to exhaust all the above mentioned values of the images.

So we can write:

$$h_m = f_p$$

This leads us to a real contradiction because the even pairs of the function f connect the even numbers of the set N only to a part of the numbers of the ordinal ω and not to all: as it should happen in the presence of a bijection between the ordinal ω and the even numbers of the set N .

Since this contradiction is produced by the functions f and h whose existence follows directly from the hypothesis of a decimal numerical system capable of representing every natural number, without any limit, this hypothesis will have to be considered false.

This means that if we want to avoid this contradiction, there must be at least one natural number that cannot be represented by the decimal numerical system. Which number will limit those that can be represented by such a system to the only ones that precede it, which will therefore be finite.

□

2 New prospects in mathematics

In the margin of this demonstration we can briefly mention that if the natural numbers are finite, the integer numbers that are the same with the addition of their opposites except zero must also be finite. Moreover, if we proceed

in a completely specular way to what we have just seen, we can demonstrate that even the rational and irrational numbers that can be represented by the decimal numerical system must be finite.

Finally, applying the procedure adopted here also in the axiomatic set theory, we immediately come to the conclusion that natural numbers, having to be finite, cannot be constructed with Peano axioms.